

KEY INDICATORS

With 8,255 hectares, Luxembourg had 6.3% of its farmland under organic management, which was below the EU average of 10.6%. Organic farmland more than quadrupled, similarly to the European Union. In Luxembourg, organic retail sales amounted to 164 million euros or 8.2% of all retail sales, considerably higher than the EU organic share.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

2,003 ha (1.6%)

8,255 ha (6.3%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

312%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

828 ha (2.4%)

3,533 ha (5.7%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

25 ha (0.7%)

152 ha (9.7%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

1,175 ha (1.8%)

4,570 ha (6.7%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

48 (1.7%)

149 (7.9%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

N/D

Processors

28

110

Importers

N/D

13

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

164 M€ (8.2%)

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

259 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

22 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN LUXEMBOURG

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on ASTA, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN LUXEMBOURG

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Biogros

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Luxembourg CAP Strategic Plan provides for a more than five-fold increase in the share of agricultural area under organic farming and expenditure on organic support by 2027 compared with 2018, with a funded target of 24% organic by 2027. Support payments per ha for fruit and vegetables are doubled compared with the previous period, with smaller increases for grapes, arable and grassland. Support for conversion is also increased to levels up to 75% higher than maintenance support, reaching 2500€/ha for permanent crops.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	5 kha	24 kha (+394%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	3.8%	19.8% (+421%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	85%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	1 M€	8 M€ (+556%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	258 €	342 € (+33%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	35 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	41 M€	20.7%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	129 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	465 M€	7.6%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	270	300	850	1200	1350
	2023	P2	400	450	2000	2500	2500
Change from 2019 to 2023			+48%	+50%	+135%	+108%	+85%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	220	250	600	800	950
	2023	P2	300	300	1150	1500	1500
Change from 2019 to 2023			+36%	+20%	+92%	+88%	+58%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+23%	+20%	+42%	+50%	+42%
	2023		+33%	+50%	+74%	+67%	+67%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Luxembourg is approaching the end of its fourth national organic action plan, with the first one started in 2009. Despite the ambitious growth targets and the high levels of support available (see above), many actions in the current plan are mainly focused on early-stage scoping of information initiatives.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2016-18	None	None
Current Action Plan	2019-25	20% of UAA by 2025	20% public procurement by 2025

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2016 - 2018)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2019 - 2025)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Luxembourg is negligible. Luxembourg was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. Organic aquaculture was not highlighted in the current or previous national organic action plans. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.